

Viscosity of Solutions of KCl and NaCl in Dioxane-water Mixtures at 40°

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The viscosities of the solutions of KCl and NaCl in 10%, 20%, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures have been measured at 40°. The data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation. ' B ' has been found to depend on the composition of the solvent.

As an extension of the previous investigations¹, the viscosities of the solutions of KCl and NaCl were measured at 10%, 20%, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures at 40°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chloride and sodium chloride (E. P., Merck) were recrystallised from triple distilled conductivity water. These were dried at 180° for 24 hr. and stored in vacuum. Preparation of the solvents and solutions and measurements of viscosity were the same as described earlier². The results of measurements are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Conc.	10% Dioxane. η/η_0		20% Dioxane. η/η_0		30% Dioxane. η/η_0	
	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.	Obs.	Calc.
Potassium chloride.						
0.1000M	1.0056	1.0058	1.0079	1.0078	1.0095	1.0094
0.0750	1.0042	1.0043	1.0065	1.0060	1.0062	1.0071
0.0500	1.0028	1.0031	1.0049	1.0043	1.0045	1.0050
0.0250	1.0016	1.0018	1.0034	1.0023	1.0030	1.0027
0.0100	1.0008	1.0009	1.0026	1.0012	1.0020	1.0013
0.0075	1.0006	1.0007	1.0023	1.0009	1.0018	1.0011
0.0050	1.0002	1.0005	..	..	1.0014	1.0007
0.0025	1.0001	1.0004	..	..	1.0013	1.0004
0.0010	0.9999	1.0002	..	..	1.0006	1.0002
Sodium chloride.						
0.1000M	1.0198	1.0188	1.0171	1.0180	1.0191	1.0185
0.0750	1.0155	1.0150	1.0122	1.0137	1.0157	1.0141
0.0500	1.0112	1.0103	1.0064	1.0095	1.0127	1.0098
0.0250	1.0054	1.0054	1.0096	1.0051	1.0115	1.0052
0.0100	1.0048	1.0023	1.0050	1.0023	1.0101	1.0024
0.0075	1.0041	1.0020	1.0040	1.0018	1.0071	1.0019
0.0050	1.0020	1.0013	1.0040	1.0012	1.0009	1.0014
0.0025	1.0013	1.0007	1.0017	1.0007	1.0007	1.0008
0.0010	1.0006	1.0003	1.0013	1.0003	1.0002	1.0004

1. Das *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 42, 166.

2. Acharya *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 36.

TABLE II

Solvent composition (wt.% of dioxane).	Potassium chloride.			Sodium chloride.			ΔB (NaCl—KCl).
	A.	B.	α .	A.	B.	α .	B
10	0.00561	0.093	1.14	0.0070	0.14	1.26	0.107
20	0.00569	0.050	1.20	0.0075	0.15	1.04	0.100
30	0.00594	0.061	1.24	0.0079	0.20	0.80	0.139

DISCUSSION

The Jones-Dole equation:

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC$$

has been found to be inadequate and the viscosity data have been examined in the light of the modified form¹:

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^\alpha$$

The constant 'A', which is associated with the interionic properties, has been calculated¹ by the expression given by Falkenhagen and Vernon^{2b}. The values of ' α ' and 'B' are estimated from the slope and intercept, respectively, of the straight line obtained by plotting $\log \{\eta/\eta_0 - (1 + A\sqrt{C})\}$ against $\log C$. Utilising these values of 'B' and ' α ', the relative viscosities have been calculated and are recorded in Table I. The agreement between the calculated and the observed values is fairly good. In Table II, the values of 'A', 'B', and ' α ' are also tabulated.

Till now no satisfactory explanation about the nature of 'B' has been advanced. The value of B for different electrolytes differs widely³. This has led to various speculations. Asmus⁴ suggested that the value of B could be determined by the lyotropic number and entropy of hydration. Frank and Evans⁵ and Latimer⁶ have established the existence of a solvation sphere of varying nature round an ion and hence 'B' varies. Asmus's lyotropic number of an ion also varies. So B is likely to be dependent on the nature of solvation sphere of ion which in mixed solvents like dioxane-water is bound to be formed by both water and dioxane. Following Frank and Evans⁵ and Latimer⁶, it may be argued that the presence of dioxane molecules in the solvation sphere would promote the ordering of structure of water and thereby an increase in viscosity will be observed, 'B' having a more positive value. Table II shows that with the increase in the dioxane content of the medium, viscosity of both the electrolyte solutions increases, causing an increase in 'B' also. This may be due either to an increase in the size of the solvated ion in presence of dioxane or to a greater ordering of the water structure in the solvation sphere or both. Data on conductance of electrolytic solutions in dioxane-water media, obtained in this laboratory (unpublished), suggest that no appreciable change in size of the ions takes place with

2a. *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, 14, 537.

3. Harned and Owen, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions".

4. *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1949, 4a, 589.

5. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 507.

6. *Chem. Rev.*, 1936, 18, 349.

increase in dioxane content of the medium. If this be so, the rise in viscosity observed in presence of dioxane is caused by the ordering of water structure in the solvation sphere.

From Table II it appears that the difference in the 'B' values (ΔB) for the pair KCl-NaCl is almost the same in 10% and 20% dioxane, but in 30% dioxane, a slight increase in ΔB is noticed.

At lower dioxane content, the 'iceberg effect' of Frank and Evans⁵ predominates, which appears to be of the same order of magnitude in the case of K^+ and Na^+ ions. But with increasing dioxane content, the dioxane molecules themselves become a part of the solvation sphere, the nature of which appears to be influenced by the nature of ions. Positive values ΔB (NaCl - KCl) would suggest a greater ordering effect of Na^+ than K^+ in so far as both water and dioxane molecules are concerned.

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